

Holistic Health: A Tool for Attaining Wellbeing in the Modern-Day World

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Abstract

Wellness is an attitude reflected in the way of life that one creates to maximize one's well-being and potential. Traditional medicine takes a holistic approach, considering man as a whole across a broad ecological range. Traditional medicine holds the strategy for providing entire healthcare coverage to the world's population while remaining acceptable, safe, and economically practical. People are turning to holistic health due to their dissatisfaction with allopathic medicine. People now understand that contemporary medications can be healing yet harmful. Each medicine has side effects, sometimes more severe than the primary impact. The wellness lifestyle concept encompasses five distinct dimensions: self-responsibility, dietary knowledge, physical fitness, stress management, and environmental sensitivity. Each of the five categories holds equal significance in achieving holistic health.

Keywords: Wellness, Wellbeing, Holistic Health

Introduction

Holistic Health

The term *holistic* comes from the Greek word 'holos', which means wholly or entirely. Holistic well-being is not a novel concept. This philosophy originated in India and China 5000 years ago and emphasized a healthy, environmentally conscious lifestyle. It is a health philosophy focused on a love of life rather than a fear of death. It fosters a high level of wellbeing across the individual's entire lifestyle. Holistic health practitioners take charge of their well-being (Aronson, 2003).

According to the holistic approach to health, it is necessary to consider each person from his mental, physical, emotional and feeling, social life, and spiritual perspectives to achieve comprehensive good health and wellbeing. This view is consistent with the conventional wisdom that maintaining a healthy body, mind, family, and environment is essential to overall wellbeing. Being as healthy as possible and having everything function as well as possible are holistic health's ultimate goals. Ideas about health have also evolved through evolution—the biological and ecological concepts developed before the psychological notion of health (Huss, 1989).

Relationship between Mind and Body

Holistic health seeks to achieve maximum wellbeing by emphasizing the interdependence of the mind, body, and spirit. It is a dynamic, self-motivating experience that assists people in living a meaningful and active lifestyle (Kalariya et al., 2023).

Indian manuscripts such as the Vedas, Upanishads, Bhagavad Gita, and Yogic and Ayurvedic traditions provide a holistic view of human existence. According to the scriptures, a person is made of "Prakriti" and "Purusha" (EkhartYoga, 2013). The Vedas and Upanishads state the body (Sharira), mind (Manas), and soul (Atman) are the mental, physical, and spiritual aspects of a person. The Bhagavad Gita emphasizes the mind and intellect, with the intellect being responsible for wisdom. The soul is eternal and beyond physical existence. Yoga and Ayurveda give practical outlines for balancing and harmonizing these aspects. Yoga can integrate the body, mind, and soul to achieve self-realization. The ultimate aim is to achieve a balance, leading to self-realization. As a result, the person is a whole person with a body, mind, and soul, and we are concerned with the person's totality. By developing a new paradigm of health treatment based on life energy rather than a pathological idea or approach, we can cater to the person as a whole (Atwal, 2010; Sumati, 2017).

Importance of Holistic Health

Holistic health is important for many reasons, but a few of them are mentioned below (Bauman & Berkeley Holistic Health Center, 1978; Ventegodt et al., 2016):

- It emphasizes internal healing as an alternative to surgery, radiation, and pharmacological therapy.
- It is tri-level (physical, emotional, and spiritual) rather than unilevel (physical only). It stresses primary prevention rather than crisis intervention. It is a long-term, ongoing, and continuous activity that is not fragmented (Minhas & Chahal, 2022).
- It acknowledges that the client is an active and dedicated partner in the healing process, not a passive recipient.
- It recognizes the importance of "What works" without requiring a thorough understanding of the underlying mechanisms.
- It fully accepts the rational scientific approach's significance as a tool for discovery, comprehension, and evaluation. Yoga, zen, religious rituals, meditation, massage, or postural training are non-scientific practices.
- It emphasizes that not all illnesses are "bad" and must be "eliminated" as soon as possible. Some symptoms indicate cleansing or the need for balance (Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2013).

Components of Well-Being

The idea of wellbeing is comprehensive and applicable in various contexts, including those involving the economy, society, psychology, and other factors (Livingston et al., 2022). According to Veenhoven (2004), the term "wellbeing" broadly "denotes that something is in a good state" even though the phrase is vague on what exactly makes up a good state.

There were two ways to define wellbeing—the traditions of hedonism and eudaimonia. The hedonic tradition emphasizes concepts like joy, pleasure, and life-fulfillment. The eudaemonic tradition defines well-being in terms of practical and advantageous psychological functioning and growth (Ryan & Deci, 2001).

There are two different kinds of wellbeing: subjective wellbeing and objective wellbeing.

Subjective Wellbeing: A person's subjective well-being is that portion of their overall wellbeing that can be assessed only by directly asking them about three different aspects of wellbeing: evaluative wellbeing (life satisfaction), hedonic wellbeing (positive emotions like happiness and sadness), and eudemonic wellbeing (a sense of purpose and meaning in life) (Western & Tomaszewski, 2016).

The three interconnected elements of subjective well-being are life satisfaction, pleasant affect, and negative affect (Pooja, 2016). Life satisfaction refers to feelings of happiness with life, and affect relates to pleasant and unpleasant moods and emotions (Diener & Suh, 1997; Dodge et al., 2012).

Objective Wellbeing: This measure of well-being examines whether a person has access to essential rights and necessities such as food, shelter, water, and medical care (Western & Tomaszewski, 2016).

Emotional wellbeing, physical wellbeing, social wellbeing, workplace wellbeing, and societal wellbeing are additional categories for wellbeing (Stoewen, 2017).

Emotional wellbeing is an individual's capacity to effectively manage stress, show resilience, and express happy feelings.

Physical wellbeing is enhancing bodily performance through exercise and a balanced diet.

Social wellbeing is effective communication, the capacity to form connections, and access to sufficient social support.

Workplace wellbeing is the capacity of individuals to advance in their career, pursue their interests and values, and find meaning and satisfaction in life.

Practices to Promote Wellbeing

Yoga and Meditation: In ancient India, yoga expanded one's consciousness, cultivated awareness, and achieved self-realization. The three main ways yoga is practiced today are asanas, postures, breathing techniques, and meditation.

The term "meditation" denotes a collection of self-regulation techniques that emphasize developing consideration and awareness to better exert voluntary control over mental processes and, as a result, promote overall mental health (Walsh & Shapiro, 2006).

People can use mindfulness meditation as a valuable tool to concentrate on their thoughts, feelings, and actions. Mindfulness entails being attentive to and attentive to the present moment or experience from moment to moment without passing judgment or assessing it (Kabat-Zinn, 2013).

Exercise and Nutrition: The food and our physical health are interconnected. However, previous research results showed that whatever we eat also affects the feelings and mental health of people. Research has also looked at the link between nutrition and mental health in children and adolescents. The subject of 'Nutritional Psychiatry' is dedicated to research on the impact of food on mental health, encompassing both physical and psychological well-being. Food is important to our well-being, and it is important to have a mindful understanding of its influence to make educated decisions about food choices (O'Neil et al., 2014).

Maintaining Work-Life Balance: Work-life balance is balancing activities linked to professional and personal lives. People must make time for enjoyment and leisure pursuits, as well as their family and friends. Splitting one's time equally between the two presents a difficult challenge for the person (Guest, 2002; Sirgy & Lee, 2017).

If a person is able to spend the same amount of time and effort on job and personal life, it does not create stress. Instead, it aims to bring the two into harmony. Understanding one's priorities is critical to attaining a healthy work-life balance, including professional priorities, work targets, career goals, job performance, and personal priorities, such as time spent with family, free time, hobbies, and socializing.

Therefore, it is up to each person to choose their priorities and harmonize their many tasks in a manner that ultimately results in personal pleasure and fulfillment. Therefore, the optimal equilibrium may vary among individuals.

Gainful Employment: In psychology, gainful employment refers to the benefits derived from work that contribute to one's well-being. Snyder et al. (2011) coined the phrase 'gainful employment' to underscore the importance of one's work in promoting well-being. Gainful employment includes the following nine elements (Snyder et al., 2011):

- Positive engagement
- Financial gain for both oneself and one's family

- Variety of work
- Achieving high performance and reaching objectives
- Secure and protected work setting
- Valuing and acknowledging diversity in the workplace
- Establishing camaraderie and loyalty among colleagues
- Companionship and loyalty at work
- A purposeful work

Human Strengths and Virtues: According to the World Health Organization (WHO), “mental health includes both achieving psychological wellbeing and the absence of disorders or mental illness”. It is “a condition of wellbeing in which one is aware of one’s capacities, able to handle life’s regular pressures, able to work successfully and fruitfully, and able to contribute to one’s community”(WHO, 2004).

So, to fully live one’s lives, one needs to focus on the potential and character traits that he or she possesses.

Peterson and Seligman (2005) devised the Values in Action (VIA) framework to classify human capacities. Strengths refer to the inherent qualities individuals possess that serve as valuable resources in attaining objectives and enhancing one’s overall health and welfare. Six distinct groups categorize the 24 character traits: bravery, compassion, intellect and erudition, fairness, self-control, and spiritual growth (Peterson et al., 2005).

Introduction to Positive Interventions: Many interventions are included under positive interventions, which can be divided into seven main categories: gratitude, savouring, meaning, empathy, kindness, optimism, and strengths (Bolier et al., 2013).

Gratitude: It entails expressing appreciation and admiration for other people or things, making one feel good. People can engage in activities like keeping a gratitude diary, writing a gratitude or thank you note, noting what went well, listing three positive things, etc., to cultivate an “attitude of thankfulness”(Arya & Khandelwal, 2014)

Savouring: (Bryant & Veroff, 2007) defined savouring as observing, appreciating, and strengthening the happy experiences of life. Savouring encourages conscious attention to all of one’s senses, including thought and emotions, as well as vision, sound, smell, taste, and touch. The primary goal of savoring is concentrating attention, being conscious of one’s sensations, and prolonging the pleasant consequences.

Meaning: Meaning serves two crucial purposes in one’s life, which makes it highly significant. One is that it offers one the groundwork one needs to be more resilient and recover from adversity, and the second is that it gives one a sense of direction that enables

one to create and accomplish one's goals and objectives. Positive interventions that emphasize meaning primarily increase a person's knowledge of what gives his life significance and what one can do to accomplish it (Kalashnikova et al., 2022).

Empathy: Being in another person's shoes allows people to view and comprehend from their point of view. Empathy is the capacity to feel what another person is experiencing. By encouraging understanding within the relationship, empathy fosters social bonds.

Kindness: Being considerate and kind to oneself and others can be a wonderful way to feel good. During kindness exercises, participants must intentionally show kindness to themselves and others. Examples of these actions include giving small gifts, donating items to those in need, providing free services like teaching others, visiting and spending time with orphan children or older people in nursing homes, forgiving oneself for mistakes and taking care of one's health (Silton, 2019).

Optimism: Optimism is the feeling of being hopeful, thinking of the positive part in a situation rather than the unpleasant part. It is also about the belief regarding the likelihood of good things happening over bad ones. So, optimism is an attitude that reflects a person's belief or hope that a task, activity, or overall outcome will be beneficial and favourable (Sharma, 2012).

Strengths: Strength is a feature that people have that energizes them, allows them to implement at their best, and, most importantly, makes them feel like "the real them." Likely, areas of strength are also those in which they excel. Strength is frequently confused with competencies, talent, or ability, but these concepts differ in positive psychology. Additionally, they will not need to force themselves to use their strengths because they will already be driven to do so (Park & Peterson, 2008).

Government Programs and Holistic Health

Ayushman Bharat

The National Health Policy recommended Ayushman Bharat in 2017, with the goal of achieving universal health coverage (UHC). To effectively handle health comprehensively, encompassing prevention, promotion, and ambulatory care, it is necessary to develop innovative programs at the primary, secondary, and tertiary levels. The National Health Authority (2019) established the Ayushman Bharat initiative to fulfill the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and its primary commitment to ensuring everyone's inclusion. Ayushman Bharat employs a continuum of maintenance approach that involves two interweaved features:

- Health and Wellness Facilities (HWCs).
- Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (PM-JAY)

Health and Wellness Facilities (HWCs)

The major objective of the HWCs is to enhance the availability of affordable and excellent healthcare services at the primary level. The purpose is to offer a wider array of services to address the primary healthcare requirements of the entire local community, thereby enhancing accessibility, inclusivity, and fairness within close proximity. Health promotion and prevention endeavors to maintain individuals' well-being by encouraging and empowering them to adopt healthy behaviors and implementing modifications that reduce the probability of acquiring chronic illnesses and morbidities (National Health Mission, 2017).

The Prime Minister Jan Arogya Yojana (PM-JAY)

The Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojna, also known as PM-JAY, is the second component of Ayushman Bharat. The implementation of this program took place on September 23rd, 2018. PM-JAY, the world's largest health assurance program, seeks to provide coverage for hospitalization in secondary and tertiary care facilities for over 10.74 crore impoverished and vulnerable families (approximately 50 crore beneficiaries). Every family receives a health benefit of Rs. 5 lakh annually.

School Health Program

The government of India has set up the "School Health Program" as portion of the Ayushman Bharat to increment interventions for illness prevention and health advancements. It is a cooperative effort between the Department of School Education & Literacy in the Ministry of Human Resource & Development and the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare (National Health Mission, 2017; Raman & Thomas, 2023).

The objectives of this programme are:

- To give kids in schools age-appropriate information about diet and health.
- To encourage children about healthy habits that will help make a healthy life in their future .
- To identify and send malnourished and anaemic children to PHCs and hospitals as needed, in order to diagnose and treat diseases in children and adolescents as early as possible.
- To encourage clean drinking water in classrooms.
- To encourage females to practise safe menstrual hygiene.
- To use Health & Wellness Ambassadors to spread the word about meditation and yoga.
- To promote research on children's nutrition, wellness, and health.

All public and private schools nationally will commence the school health promotion programs. It is accomplished via the combined efforts and close cooperation of the

Department of School Education and Literacy, the Ministry of Human Resource and Development at all levels, and The Ministry of Health and Family Welfare. The Program was created with the help of the knowledge and insights gained from numerous international and domestic school-based interventions(NHM, 2024).

Each school will have two tutors labelled as "Health and Wellness Ambassadors," preferably one male teacher and one female teacher. These teachers will receive weekly training to share knowledge on illness prevention and health promotion for an hour through engaging activities. Students will serve as Health and Wellness Messengers in society. Therefore, these health promotion messages will also improve health behaviors nationwide. Health and Wellness Day may be observed in schools every Tuesday.

Conclusion

Holistic health comes from ancient India and China, and holistic health methods consider the interconnectedness of mind, body, and spirit in a holistic approach to well-being. Holistic health emphasizes preventive, internal healing, and patient participation in health care, unlike allopathic treatment, which typically treats symptoms and has serious side effects. This method balances physical, mental, emotional, social, and spiritual components for a meaningful life.

Yoga, meditation, and dietary awareness promote overall wellbeing by improving holistic health (physical and mental health). Exercise, work-life balance, and employment contribute to happiness and meaning.

The positive psychology intervention is about fostering human traits and virtues and practicing gratitude, savouring, empathy, and kindness to improve emotional and psychological wellbeing. These habits improve individual and societal health.

Ayushman Bharat and the School Health Program in India emphasize holistic health by integrating wellness into teaching and offering complete health care. These initiatives encourage healthy lifestyles in children for long-term population advantages.

In conclusion, implementing a holistic approach to health is essential for a changing world. Holistic health focuses on the complete person rather than symptoms, fosters a balance, and overcomes traditional medicine's limits. People can improve their wellbeing, health and community by adopting holistic health practices.

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